

MWCNT-chitosan composite chemically modified electrode as an electrochemical detector for highly selective flow injection analysis of H₂O₂

Prakasam Gayathri and Annamalai Senthil Kumar*

Environmental and Analytical Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences,
Vellore Institute of Technology University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : askumarchem@yahoo.com

Abstract : Multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT)-chitosan (CHIT) chemically modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE), designated as GCE/MWCNT-CHIT has been developed by modifying a suspension of MWCNT + CHIT-acetic acid mixture on a cleaned GCE and demonstrated as a selective electrochemical detector (ECD) for flow-injection analysis (FIA) of hydrogen peroxide. The GCE/MWCNT-CHIT showed stable surface confined redox feature at $E^{0'} = -0.22$ V vs Ag/AgCl with surface excess value $13.63 \text{ nmol cm}^{-2}$ in pH 7 PBS. Under an optimal condition, applied potential = -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl, hydrodynamic flow rate = 0.75 mL min^{-1} and pH 7 phosphate buffer as a carrier solution, the FIA-ECD showed H₂O₂ calibration plot in an range 50–2500 μM with detection limit and current sensitivity values $9.7 \mu\text{M}$ and $0.59 \text{ nA } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$ ($0.8345 \text{ A M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) respectively. There was no interference from cysteine, ascorbic acid, uric acid, nitrite, and nitrate. A cosmetic cream, clinical H₂O₂ and milk were further tested as real samples with $\sim 100\%$ recovery values.

Keywords : Carbon nanotube, chitosan, electrochemical detector, real sample.

Introduction

Selective determination of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is important in several areas including food, pharmaceutical, industrial and environmental testing^{1–4}. H₂O₂ is a main product of enzyme catalysed reaction and involved with various biological processes such as immune cell activation, vascular remodelling, apoptosis, stomatal closure and root growth etc.⁵. Exposure of high concentration of H₂O₂ ($> 1 \text{ M}$) irritates skin and harms the human health⁶. So far various analytical techniques were reported for the detection of H₂O₂. Those techniques are; spectrophotometric, fluorescence, coulometric, polarographic and titrimetric techniques⁴. These methods are generally time consuming and suffer from serious interferences. On the other hand, flow injection analysis coupled electrochemical detection (FIA-ECD) offers simple, rapid and low working volume ($10 \mu\text{L}$) based detection approach^{7,8}. Here in, we introduce a new FIA-ECD technique, in which a impure multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT)-chitosan (CHIT) chemically modified glassy carbon electrode (designated as GCE/MWCNT-CHIT) used as a detector, for selective hydrogen peroxide measurement in a physiological pH.

Previously, numerous MWCNT-redox mediators based chemically modified electrodes (CMEs) have been reported for electrochemical detection of H₂O₂^{9–13}. However, very limited reports were available with FIA-ECD techniques^{14–18}. Maintaining appreciable stability of CME under the hydrodynamic condition is a major problem with above CMEs. In further, most of the redox mediator-CMEs are unstable in physiological pH (e.g. Prussian blue analogues)^{15,16}.

Chitosan (CHIT) is a linear polysaccharide and naturally occurring biopolymer with attractive chemical properties¹⁹. Previously, functionalized MWCNT+CHIT modified thin film system for the electrochemical sensing of H₂O₂ was reported²⁰. Note that, the above modified electrode was prepared through covalent interaction between the amino group of CHIT and -OH functional group of functionalized MWCNT²⁰. Recently our group reported preparation, characterization and electrocatalytic H₂O₂ reduction of impure-MWCNT+CHIT chemically modified electrode²¹. In aim to extend to various H₂O₂ real sample analyses we further extend our studies with FIA-ECD, in this work.

Experimental

Chemicals, reagents and instrumentation :

MWCNT, (> 90% carbon basis, outer diameter : 10–15 nm; inner diameter : 2–6 nm; length 0.1–10 μm) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrogen peroxide was obtained from Rankem, India and stored in a refrigerator. Other chemicals used were all of analytical grade and used without further purification. Sodium di-hydrogen phosphate and di-sodium hydrogen phosphate were used to prepare pH 7 phosphate buffer solution (PBS) were obtained from SRL, India. All the solutions were prepared using deionized and alkaline KMnO_4 distilled (DD) water.

Voltammetric measurements were carried out with CHI models 440B (for CV) and 760D (for FIA) electrochemical workstation (USA). The three-electrode system consisted of a glassy carbon (Tokai, Japan, 3 mm diameter, 0.0707 cm^2 area), or of a chemically modified form, as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode, and a platinum wire as the auxiliary electrode. The FIA system consisted of Hitachi L-2130 pump delivery (Japan), a Rehodyne model 7125 sample injection valve (20 μL loop) with interconnecting Teflon tube and a conventional electrochemical detector system (BAS, USA).

Procedures :

A stock solution of CHIT (0.5 wt %) was prepared by mixing CHIT flakes (50 mg) with 1% glacial acetic acid (10 mL), stirred for 3 h at RT until complete dissolution, and the pH was adjusted to 4–5 using a concentrated NaOH solution. GCE/MWCNT-CHIT was prepared by sonicating a mixture of MWCNT (1 mg) and the 0.5 wt % CHIT (500 μL) for 15 min, 10 μL of above aliquot drop coated on GCE and followed by the continuous potential cycling between -0.7 to 0.7 V vs Ag/AgCl. Clinical H_2O_2 , cosmetic and milk samples purchased from a health centre, VIT University and local departmental store were subjected to real sample analyses.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical and electrocatalytic behaviours of GCE/MWCNT-CHIT :

CV response of GCE/MWCNT-CHIT at $v = 50$ mV s^{-1} is displayed in Fig. 1A and B. It showed a well-defined redox peak at apparent standard potential $E^0 =$

-0.22 V vs Ag/AgCl (A1/C1) which corresponds to a redox behaviour of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ site of impure-Fe : NH_2 -CHIT complex system²¹. Calculated surface excess (Γ) value is 13.63 nmol cm^{-2} . Ten continuous CV measurements ($n=10$) yielded a relative standard deviation (RSD) value 0.78%. Control experiments with GCE/MWCNT (curve b) and GCE/CHIT (curve c) were failed to show any such redox features like the GCE/MWCNT-CHIT case! GCE/MWCNT-CHIT's redox behaviour is an adsorption controlled electron transfer in nature (plot of peak current vs scan rate is linear, data not given) and obeys pH dependent Nernstian feature (plot of E_{pc} vs pH is linear and the slope value of -33 mV/decade , data not shown).

Fig. 1C displays CV of GCE/MWCNT-CHIT without (curve a) and with 500 μM of H_2O_2 (curve b) in pH 7 PBS. A marked increase in cathodic peak current at -0.16 V vs Ag/AgCl, where the A1/C1 redox peak exist, indicates efficient electro-catalytic behaviour of the working electrode to H_2O_2 reduction reaction (curve b). Meanwhile, the unmodified electrodes, GCE/MWCNT (curve c) and GCE/CHIT (curve d) were also subjected to H_2O_2 reduction studies. Unfortunately, the electrochemical behaviours showed reduction peaks at high negative potentials. This observation indicates large over-potentials for the H_2O_2 reduction reaction on the control electrodes unlike to the GCE/MWCNT-CHIT case.

Flow injection analysis of H_2O_2 :

H_2O_2 electrochemical sensing was demonstrated using FIA-ECD detector composed of GCE/MWCNT-CHIT system at an applied potential and hydrodynamic flow rate -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl and 0.75 mL/min respectively along with pH 7 PBS as a carrier solution. Under the optimal condition, Fig. 2A (curve a) shows a typical FIA response of increasing concentration of H_2O_2 from 50 to 5000 μM . Each concentration was injected three times to endorse the stability of the ECD. Systematic increase in the current signal against the increasing in H_2O_2 concentration was noticed. We propose the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ redox species formed due to impure (iron)-MWCNT + CHIT ($-\text{NH}_2$) interaction is responsible for the electrocatalytic and sensing of H_2O_2 . In order to validate the observation, a non-functionalized polymer, sol-gel is combined with impure MWCNT and modified on GCE for further testing. As can be seen in Fig. 2A (curve b), no marked signal for

Fig. 1. (A) Schematic illustration for the preparation of GCE/MWCNT-CHIT complex. (B) Ten continuous CV responses of GCE/MWCNT-CHIT. (C) CV responses of GCE/MWCNT-CHIT with 500 μM H₂O₂ and its control systems.

H₂O₂ injections were observed unlike to the optimal case with specific FIA signals. This particular experimental result confirms the complexation between the iron in impure MWCNT with CHIT and further to H₂O₂ electrochemical sensing. Ten successive injections of 50 μM H₂O₂ give a reproducible current response with relative standard deviation (RSD) value 5% (curve c). Obtained linear calibration range was from 50 to 2500 μM H₂O₂ with a sensitivity of 0.59 nA/μM (inset plot, Fig. 2A (curve d)). Calculated detection limit (signal to noise ratio value = 3) value is 9.7 μM. This value is comparable with the value 5 μM on HRP/Au-chitosan/ITO detector¹⁴. Effect of interference from various bio-chemicals such as cysteine (CySH), ascorbic acid (AA), uric acid (UA), nitrate (NO₃⁻) and nitrite (NO₂⁻) were also examined on GCE/MWCNT-CHIT (Fig. 2B). Interestingly, the hybrid electrode was tolerable for the above chemicals unlike to

the HRP/Au-chitosan/ITO detector with serious CySH interference (due to the gold)¹⁴. These results indicate highly selective detection of H₂O₂ on GCE/MWCNT-CHIT modified electrode in this work.

Real sample analysis :

Finally, we tested unknown H₂O₂ content present in three real samples, viz. clinical H₂O₂, cosmetic (Fig. 2C) and milk by standard addition approach. Table 1 shows real sample analysis data. After dilution factor correction, detected H₂O₂ values in the milk, clinical H₂O₂ and cosmetic samples are 0, 88.75 and 1.25 μM respectively. Note that pasteurized milk sample didn't show any original current signal. This observation implies absence of any added H₂O₂ as adulterant in the sample. However, standard addition of H₂O₂ in the milk shows the systematic increase in the FIA current signal. The recovery values of all samples are closer to 100%.

Fig. 2. (A) Flow injection analysis (FIA) responses of (a) GCE/MWCNT-CHIT, (b) GCE/MWCNT-sol-gel with different concentration of H₂O₂ spiking, (c) reproducible current response of ten continuous spiking of H₂O₂ and (d) calibration plot of [H₂O₂] vs I. (B) Interference effect and (C) Real sample analysis on GCE/MWCNT-CHIT at $E_{app} = -0.2$ V versus Ag/AgCl, $H_f = 0.75$ mL/min and pH 7 PB as a carrier solution.

Table 1. Results of the H₂O₂ real sample analysis obtained using a GCE/MWCNT-CHIT detector in FIA

Sr. no.	Parameters	Clinical H ₂ O ₂	Cosmetic	Milk
1.	Linear equation	$y = 20.9x + 2050$	$y = 48.8x + 274.7$	$y = 40.7x + 378.5$
2.	Original/detected (μM)	88.75	1.25	–
3.	Spiked (μM)	100	5	40
4.	Detected (μM)	96.7	4.82	40.2
5.	Recovery (%)	96.8	96.4	100.5
6.	Net (H ₂ O ₂)	17.7 mM	87.6 μM	–

Conclusion

A suspension of impure-MWCNT, chitosan and acetic acid mixture chemically modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE/MWCNT-CHIT) showed high selective electrocatalytic reduction of H₂O₂ in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution. Using GCE/MWCNT-CHIT as an electrochemical detector, a new flow injection analysis technique was developed for low volume detection of H₂O₂ in real samples. Flow injection analysis condition was systematically optimized. Under the optimal condition the system exhibited high sensitive and selective FIA response without any interference from cysteine, uric acid, nitrate, nitrite and ascorbic acid, unlike to the most of the metal based electrochemical detector with serious interference from cysteine, uric acid and ascorbic acid. Applicability of the method was tested by analyzing H₂O₂ contents in various real samples such as milk, cosmetic and clinical H₂O₂. Appreciable results with ~100% recovery values were noticed.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge to the Department of Science and Technology-Technology System Development (DST-TSD), India for the financial support.

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